

FEATURES OF AUTOPLAY AND ISPRING PROGRAMS

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Abstract: In this article, you will be acquainted with the capabilities of AutoPlay and Ispring programs, the backup area, its options, file extensions.

Keywords: multimedia, AutoPlay, Ispring, CD, DVD, Autorun, program, Media Studio.

To create powerful, perfect multimedia documents that meet the requirements of the time, the standard multimedia programs of Windows are not enough. For this reason, in recent years, a lot of software for creating and using multimedia documents have been developed. One of them is AutoPlay.

AutoPlay Media Studio: is a visual package with a wide range of possibilities for combining many files or sets of files into one media, creating an Autorun menu for CDs or DVDs.

Using AutoPlay Media Studio to create applications based on multimedia technologies provides a simple and convenient interface for users.

Almost no programming is required when working with AutoPlay Media Studio. The user can only use several ready-made project templates to choose a software environment with different designs.

In order to organize such an application environment in a design-rich state, the AutoPlay software tool contains ready-made objects, which include a command button, a sound amplifier, a tool that ensures the printing of files on a printer, and a number of functional objects that open and refer to Web sites.

AutoPlay Media Studio creates all the necessary files for creating graphical shells of applications and automatically launching them. Users only have to create ready-made projects for burning hard drives and CDs.

Autoplay Media Studio can easily process documents created in a number of systems, such as Visual Basic, Visual C, Java, Macromedia Flash. With the help of the program, you can not only quickly create an animated menu, directory tree, database and similar objects, but also manage them.

Autostart windows may be created in any form (form) using masks from its library. As such a mask, files in formats such as. jpg, bmp and png may also be used.

In addition, the fact that the program can burn the data to a CD or DVD while preparing the data for CD shows how extensive the capabilities of Autoplay Media Studio are.

The finished project may be created as a file with the extension .exe in the form of an unzipped archive or in a separate folder on the hard disk.

In addition, the program includes the ability to check the spelling of the text. This property of the program works together with its objects such as Label, Paragraph and Button. If the program was installed on the computer with the full version, its library may contain a very large number of dictionaries for orthographic checking of the text. So, the new version of AutoPlay Media Studio was produced with the following features:

1. Creation of auto-starting private menu, interactive presentations, multimedia applications, software applications in a few minutes;
2. The project includes various photography, music, video, animation, text and features to attach others;
3. Advanced tools for creating web applications;
4. Ability to work with XML, SQL and encryption mechanisms;
5. Ability to work with RTF format documents;
6. Ability to work with a slide show;
7. Availability of Radio Button object to change text color;
8. Extended function of printing;
9. Ability to format objects;
10. Availability of a search engine using keywords;
11. Ability to write to compact discs such as CD, DVD, etc.

Ispring program:

One of the widely used software for creating multimedia e-learning courses is the Ispring program. ISpring has the following features:

- the ability to convert presentation files in several (exe, swf, html) formats;
- the ability to insert external resources (audio, video or flash files) into the presentation content;
- protection of the content of the presentation: viewing with a password, "protecting" the presentation, "turning" the presentation only in authorized domains;
- add video and synchronize it with animations;

- a tool is installed for creating electronic tests (controls) and creating interactive texts with the ability to send their results to e-mail or to a distance learning system (LMS) (Quiz button);
- create SCORM/AICC compliant courses for use in the distance learning system;
- ActionScript API for presentation application-level scrolling;
- recording a video and synchronizing it with a presentation;
- Possibility to include YouTube videos in the content of the presentation.

• The iSpring QuizMaker software can be used to create electronic quizzes within e-learning resources.

- ISpring QuizMaker has the following main features:
- create branched tests;
- closed test questions with two, three, pie or five answers, one of which is true and two of which are closer to the truth;
- closed test tasks with multiple answers, open test tasks;
- tasks aimed at identifying similarities;
- there are opportunities to create tasks designed to determine the correct sequence.

• ISpring Free is a proprietary software that allows you to convert. PPT, PPTX, .PPS, PPSX files to Flash (SWF) and HTML5 format.

Through the program, users can insert Flash-rollers and YouTube-video resources into PowerPoint presentation slides.

In particular:

Provides the ability to transfer the created e-learning content to SCORM and TinCan systems, which means that it can be integrated with an optional LMS (Learning management system);

It is possible to compress the size of the presentation file created in PowerPoint up to 97%;

ensures the protection of the presentation file created in the PowerPoint program; iSpring Free is absolutely free.

In addition to iSpring Free, there is also iSpring Suite, which has more features and allows you to create high-quality e-learning content.

Using the tools of iSpring Suite (QuizMaker, iSpring Visuals, iSpring DialogTrainer) you can create electronic textbooks, video lectures, electronic control

tests through QuizMaker, quizzes, iSpring DialogTrainer - networked dialog electronic courses and online presentations.

It allows adding audio and video files to the created electronic course, recording audio and video, synchronizing with presentation slides, selecting various players of the electronic course, editing, printing in SCORM and TinCan standards, exporting in mp4 video format.

In addition, it is possible to create 3D books, timelines, glossaries through iSpring Visuals. It is possible to integrate courses created through iSpring with LMS.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of e-learning resources:
students have the opportunity to use resources not only during classes, but also outside of classes;
creative thinking is achieved by using e-learning resources independently;
e-learning resources, the teacher accompanies the child in performing laboratory and independent work;
by being interested in training, conditions are created to learn science better;
students will have the opportunity to independently fill in the knowledge that they could not acquire during the course of the lesson.

Based on the conclusions and recommendations made above, if AutoPlay and iSpring programs are used in the organization of the educational process, the quality of education will increase.

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